

EFFICIENCY OF USING MODERN MANAGEMENT METHODS IN MANAGEMENT OF ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the issues of targeted use of modern management methods in the management of enterprises, comprehensive assessment of management efficiency on the basis of intensive indicators and ensuring the intensive development of enterprises by increasing investment capacity and improving modern management systems.

Introduction

In the context of globalization and integration of the world economy, withstanding the growing competition, compliance with its requirements, the effective use of advanced technologies and innovations require the effective use of modern management methods of business entities. Compliance with the requirements, trends and processes in this area will allow for the integrated development of real sector enterprises, in particular, the economy of industry, agriculture and services, expanding and expanding the range of exports and

achieving sustainable economic development. Indeed, the current situation requires that "the share of industry in the gross domestic product (GDP) of developed countries is 40.0%, the share of agriculture is 5.0% and the share of services is more than 50.0%."

There is a lot of research around the world on the targeted use of modern management methods in the management of enterprises, a comprehensive assessment of management effectiveness on the basis of intensive indicators and investment capacity building. Attention is also paid to ensuring the intensive

development of enterprises through the improvement of modern management systems, improving the management methodology of modern management, the use of innovative methods of systematic analysis. The development of innovative activities of enterprises in the world and their modern management, as well as structural changes in the economies of leading countries and the further improvement of relations are among the main scientific trends of our time.

- Literature review

The issues of innovative development and management of enterprises have been studied by many foreign scholars. In particular, foreign scientists A. Show, K.R. Macconel, S.L. Brew, A. Smith, R. Tucker, M. Porter, Y. Shumpeter [3] and others have conducted research in this area. From the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) the role of innovation in the economic development of enterprises, the impact of various innovations on the dynamics of socio-economic reforms, fundamental research in management L.I. Abalkin, I. Ansoff, V.P. Baranchev, V.P. Krasovsky, R. Researched by A. Fatkhudinov, V.G. Gruzinov, Sh.I. Gizatullin, V.D. Gribov, M. Khuchek [4] and others. Issues of management of enterprises of different forms of ownership in Uzbekistan N.K. Yuldashev, B.K. Goyibnazarov, S.S. Gulomov, E.H. Mahmudov, M.K. Paradaev, B. Kamiljanov, E.A. Akramov, A. Artikov, F. Karimov, Researched in the scientific works of SN Khamraeva, R.H. Ergashev, A.M. Kadyrov [5] and others. However, in the scientific research of the above-named scientists, it is limited to the general methodological features of innovative management of enterprises. In our study, the issues of

innovative management of enterprises based on the application of modern management methods are scientifically studied.

- Research Methodology

Methods such as scientific observation, logical thinking, conversation, comparative analysis, correlation-regression analysis, expert evaluation were used in the research process.

The scientific novelty of the research is: The system of organizational and economic indicators of enterprise management has been improved, taking into account the involvement of factors of production, territorial affiliation and levels of management complexity in the assessment of economic potential; a step-by-step approach to resource management in the chain of "research and education system - inter-institutions - value creators" has been developed to create a flexible system of sustainable development of enterprises aimed at ensuring synergetic efficiency; the strategic management system of enterprises has been improved on the basis of science and technology potential, the use of resource-saving technologies and clusters; the method of integrated assessment of the effectiveness of enterprise management has been improved on the basis of their level of economic development, territorial distribution of regions, access to resources and the use of innovative development programs.

- Analysis and results

A system of organizational and economic indicators for managing the economic potential of enterprises has been developed, taking into account the application of internal and external factors, territorial affiliation and levels of

management complexity; a step-by-step approach to creating a flexible system aimed at increasing the synergetic efficiency of strategic management of enterprises is proposed; developed proposals to increase the effectiveness of strategic management of enterprises through the use of modern management methods; the method of integrated assessment of management effectiveness in enterprises has been improved through the use of targeted programs.

The expediency of the methodological approach and methods used in the research is explained by the widespread use of statistical data of enterprises in the economy, the use of modern research methods and theoretical developments in solving practical problems, as well as practical testing of conclusions, recommendations and recommendations.

The scientific significance of the results of the study is that the proposals and recommendations developed on their basis can be used to increase the effectiveness of strategic management in enterprises, the introduction of special research to improve management decision-making mechanisms and evaluate the effectiveness of investments.

The practical significance of the research results is explained by the theoretical and methodological basis for assessing the effectiveness of strategic management of enterprises, the improvement of theoretical and methodological mechanisms of strategic management and their application in enterprise management.

An analysis of the work of foreign and domestic researchers has shown a great diversity of definitions of the concept of "modern management". However, each of

the interpretations is one of the foundations of this concept of modern management activity, for example, the stages of the target management process, the process of identifying and establishing relationships with the environment based on forecasts, controls and feedback, etc. structures are distinguished by their in-depth study. However, it does not fully and comprehensively define the essence of modern management, which fully embodies the distinctive features of this type of management activity.

The article offers an authorial definition of modern management. The basic criteria for this management activity are reflected. According to this definition: "Modern management is an activity consisting of the development and implementation of decisions based on continuous comparative analysis and forecasting of current trends, important factors of the internal and external environment of these facilities in order to ensure effective development." This definition clearly describes the full description of the characteristics (criteria) that characterize the management activity in the enterprise, based on this or that aspect.

The modern management system envisages the study of retrospective indicators of the future activity of the enterprise and their determination on the basis of the application of the method of extrapolation. Extrapolation is the introduction of trends established in the past to the future. In other words, in the development of the forecast, the conditions of the enterprise will not worsen in the future. This means that the outcome of the enterprise is better than in the past. This is the manifestation of the trend that

increases the level of development of the enterprise [7].

To assess the future sustainability of the enterprise, a complex integrated indicator representing the development trend (trend) is used; an expanded system of indicators is used for in-depth analysis and identification of reserves. Thus, assessing the future sustainability of an enterprise involves assessing different aspects of the entity's operations. Moreover, such an assessment is made in dynamics and in space.

At present, the development of the enterprise can be achieved only through the continuous introduction of innovations. Defining the role of innovation in helping companies achieve a competitive advantage, M. Porter noted that "...

companies gain a competitive advantage through innovation. They approach newly introduced procedures in a broad sense, using both new technologies and new ways of working. Once a company has gained a competitive advantage due to innovation, it can maintain these advantages only with the help of regular improvements. Competitors will immediately and surely bypass any company that stops improving and implementing innovations" [8].

The article assesses the factors that affect the sustainability of the enterprise. Table 1 analyzes the main innovation trends in enterprises and the factors that negatively affect the introduction of innovations, as well as the factors that ensure the development and support of innovations in research.

Table 1.

Analysis of factors influencing the effectiveness of modern management of enterprises [10].

№	factors	effects of factors
1	knowledge and skills	Lack of knowledge and skills in the field of management (laws of the market economy) in manufacturing enterprises hinders the introduction of innovative management.
2	degree of centralization	the high level of centralization limits the ability of lower-level managers to think creatively and take a creative approach to management.
3	communication system	the communication system is not well organized or the manager is unable to use them effectively, which in some cases leads to the problem of untimely arrival of information and news.
4	contractual relationship	the manager's and employee's lack of clear knowledge and adherence to assigned tasks hinders the development of the management process.
5	interest in innovation	low interest in innovation by managers, i.e. lack of flexibility in management.
6	incentive	the incomplete development of the incentive system in management reduces the interest in introducing innovative management.

The introduction of innovative technologies in the activities of enterprises,

the use of strategic management methods will increase efficiency and increase production.

According to the results of the analysis, in order to introduce strategic management of innovative activities of enterprises, first of all, to improve the knowledge, skills, abilities of management staff, reduce the level of centralization and the introduction of new information technologies in the information exchange system. The exit serves to reduce the level of informal communication, ensuring that each manager has a clear and complete understanding of the tasks assigned to him and perform them in a timely manner.

The article evaluates the ways and factors to increase the efficiency of the enterprise. Improving production efficiency is a constant task of the company's management. In our opinion, the solution of this task in practice depends on the following factors:

- selection of the optimal production process, providing the maximum volume of production at the lowest cost in the production of high quality products that meet market requirements;

- sales of products aimed at meeting consumer demand and high income (profit);

- creation of optimal production reserves, which allows to save working capital.

Organizational and economic factors, including management, play an important role in increasing the efficiency of production activities of enterprises. Their importance increases with the growth of production and the complexity of economic relations. These factors include, first and foremost, the creation of rational forms of production and the improvement of

existing ones - concentration, specialization, cooperation and combination. In management, they are expressed in the improvement of methods and forms of management, planning, economic incentives, ie the whole economic mechanism of the enterprise.

The process associated with the production of new products or the improvement of existing ones as a result of human scientific and technical activity is an innovative activity. The results of the introduction of innovation will allow companies to have a significant competitive advantage, which will be a serious incentive for the enterprise. World experience shows that enterprises are interested in the introduction of resource-saving advances in science. Secondly, as a result of this global event, the opportunities to further increase the investment attractiveness of the country's enterprises through further development of their potential, and thirdly, the development of sustainable and quality products through radical diversification of enterprises and radically increase efficiency.

Innovative management and increasing the efficiency of production of innovative products and services will ensure economic growth, changes in key macro-microeconomic indicators. Therefore, the study analyzed the double correlation coefficients between the volume of innovative products and services created and key economic indicators. According to the calculations, the volume of created innovative products, works and services has a high correlation with all sectors of the economy. Therefore, the study analyzed the double correlation coefficients between the volume of

innovative products and services created and key economic indicators.

According to the calculations, the volume of created innovative products, works and services has a high correlation with all sectors of the economy.

The lowest figure corresponds to industry contribution, which is 0.71. The role of budget allocations in the creation of innovative products and services is also significant. The double correlation coefficient between them was found to be 0.76. It is clear that the creation of

innovative products and services will ensure economic growth in the economy and industries.

In order to determine the impact of investment in innovation in industrial enterprises of the country on the economic development of the industry and labor productivity, regression equations based on the dynamics of data for 2000-2019 were used (Table 2).

Table 2

Correlation equations between investment in innovation in industrial enterprises and key economic indicators [11].

No	regression equation	t-statistics	p-value	R ²
1	$Y=33657.6+5.5795L+0.87982I$ (6254.66) (0.682) (0.178)	$a_0=-5.38$ $a_1=8.20$ $a_2=4.94$	0.000 0.000 0.000	0.98
2	$\ln Y=9.6420+2.0488\ln L+0.11357\ln I$ (1.698) (0.2126) (0.0351)	$a_0=-5.67$ $a_1=9.63$ $a_2=3.23$	0.000 0.000 0.000	0.98
3	$Y/L=1.9308+1.6831I/L$ (0.1168) (0.1359)	$a_0=16.52$ $a_1=12.38$	0.000 0.000	0.89
4	$\ln Y/\ln L=0.846171+0.290909\ln I/\ln L$ (0.025) (0.026)	$a_0=-33.71$ $a_1=10.99$	0.000 0.000	0.87

Note: Y - gross output of the industry in billion soums; I - the amount of expenditures on innovations, in billions of soums; L - annual number of workers and employees, thousand people; Y / L - labor productivity in industrial enterprises, in million soums.

The t-statistics and p-values, which statistically represent the determined coefficients of the equations at the level of demand, indicate that they are at the level of demand. Also, the fact that the detected R² indicator is close together showed that there is a high correlation between the indicators. According to the equations, the

production of industrial products in 2000 - 2019 was due to the involvement of more labor resources, labor productivity increased due to the involvement of high-capacity technologies in production.

This means that in order to achieve the goals set out in the Action Strategy, it is necessary to widely introduce innovations in all enterprises, including industrial enterprises, to apply modern management methods in management.

The elasticity calculated in the article shows that the increase in the amount of investment and the amount of funds allocated by the state budget for science

will increase the cost of innovation, to ensure sustainable economic development.

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the results of improving the efficiency of the use of modern management methods in the management of enterprises, the following conclusions were made:

1. Management system is one of the important factors in achieving production efficiency and strengthening the economic potential of the enterprise. In today's market relations, the management system must, first of all, ensure the stability of the enterprise, reduce economic risk, promote the production of quality and competitive products. It should also serve to increase the level of interest of employees in the results of their work, to prevent non-production costs and losses, and to strengthen labor and production discipline.

2. In order to achieve efficiency in the management of the enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to clearly define the goals of management, as well as the means and ways to achieve them. The production of high-quality and competitive products at

the lowest cost, which is the main task of the enterprise, ensures maximum profitability and prevents it from falling into crisis.

3. The study analyzed the trends and patterns of operation of enterprises and identified the need to increase its competitiveness based on the principles of strategic management. Sustainability is the efficiency of the enterprise, the realization of its competitive potential, and competitiveness is the determination of the ability of the enterprise to effectively use its production capacity and sell competitive products. Therefore, the logical interdependence of these concepts, taking into account their interaction, allows the company to form an optimal strategy to increase competitiveness.

4. The modern management process allows to diagnose the state of management in the implementation of this process in the practice of enterprises and to identify decisions to achieve the set goals based on the classification of existing problems. At the same time, the main goal should be to ensure the sustainability of the enterprise.

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